

THEMATIC SECTION: 41ST ANNUAL SCIENTIFIC MEETING OF THE ASSOCIATION OF EMBRYO TECHNOLOGY IN EUROPE (AETE)
SUPEROVULATION, OPU-IVP, AND EMBRYO TRANSFER

Long-term blood plasma biochemical analysis in pigs derived from assisted reproductive technologies.

Małgorzata Mikita¹, Jon Romero-Aguirregomezcorta², Sebastián Cánovas¹, Sonia Heras¹, Guillermo Ramis³, Joaquín Gadea¹, Pilar Coy¹, Raquel Romar¹

¹Department of Physiology, Universidad de Murcia, International Excellence Campus for Higher Education and Research (Campus Mare Nostrum), Murcia, Spain Institute for Biomedical Research of Murcia (IMIB), Murcia, Spain

²Department of Anatomy and Comparative Pathological Anatomy, Universidad de Murcia, International Excellence Campus for Higher Education and Research (Campus Mare Nostrum), Murcia, Spain Institute for Biomedical Research of Murcia (IMIB), Murcia, Spain

³Department of Animal Production, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, International Excellence Campus for Higher Education and Research (Campus Mare Nostrum), University of Murcia, ³⁰100 Murcia, Spain

E-mail: mi.mikita@um.es

Rising livestock demand has increased use of assisted reproductive technologies (ART). Evidence indicates long-term effects of ART on molecular physiology and metabolism. This study explores ART's impact on biochemical parameters in a colony of pigs from 1 to 5 years of age. Animals were born after artificial insemination (AI) and transfer of embryos *in vitro* produced with (RF-IVP) or without (C-IVP) oviductal and uterine fluids during *in vitro* fertilization and embryo culture media (Paris-Oller et al., J Anim Sci and Biotechnol, 2021). Pigs were maintained under identical conditions and sampled every six months. Number of animals in each group decreased throughout life: 33 to 9 (AI); 22 to 10 (C-IVP); and 14 to 4 (RF-IVP). The number of blood samples was the same as the number of animals and were collected via jugular venipuncture in lithium heparin tubes and immediately transported to laboratory. Plasma was obtained through centrifugation (1200 g, 20 min, 4°C, Eppendorf 5810 R) of blood collected via direct jugular venipuncture in lithium heparin tubes. Plasma was assessed using a chemistry analyzer (Olympus AU400, Japan) for creatinine (CREA), urea, amylase, creatine kinase (CK), cholesterol, alkaline phosphatase (ALP), gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT), glucose, aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), lipase, total protein (TP), albumin (ALB), globulin (GLOB), triglycerides (TRIGL), and total bilirubin (TBIL). Data were analyzed by mixed-effects model and likelihood-ratio test to determine effects of age, group and sex on the variables. Post-hoc test for multiple comparisons Tukey's method was used. Statistical significance was set at $P < 0.05$. Age significantly influenced all variables. Glucose, cholesterol, lipase, CK, ALP, AST, ALT were not affected by any other variable. TP, GLOB, UREA and TRIGL showed progressive elevation with age, with peak values between 4-5 years. ALB, cholesterol, CK, ALP, AST, GGT exhibited characteristic juvenile decline, with ALP and AST showing reduction during early development (155 to 52 U/L and 121 to 37 U/L respectively) followed by stabilization, while ALT displayed oscillatory changes. Glucose and TBIL showed initial elevation peaking at 2 years, before decreasing. CREA and amylase fluctuated irregularly. Critical developmental transitions occurred at 1.5-2 years and 4-5 years, representing key physiological maturation milestones. ALBU showed the highest mean concentration in the RF-IVP group and lowest in the AI group, while GGT showed the opposite pattern. ALBU, GLOB and urea were influenced by sex, with females higher ALBU and urea levels, while males showed elevated GLOB values. Long-term results confirm slight persisting biochemical differences in naturally and artificially conceived pigs, although the clinical relevance is unnoticeable.

This study is part of project PID2020-113366RB-I00 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033/ and "FEDER Una manera de hacer Europa". MM was funded by AFRODITA, which was funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under the MSCA Doctoral Network grant agreement No 101120126. SH was funded by IJC2019-039404-I.

Keywords: porcine, metabolism, ART